

Restoring the Traditional Linkage between Samaritan and Foreign Dating

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I. The purpose of this investigation

There is unending confusion over the traditional Samaritan dating of historical events in modern academic writing. This has caused confusion over the real dates of important historical events. Most authors rely on Chronicle Adler, a composition in Hebrew made in 1900. This book relies on older books that are accessible, but it can be seen that this is unknown by most authors, even though it has been common knowledge since the book was published in 1901. Information is often changed to suit the author and dates are changed without evidence according to his own reckoning. This article shows where the traditional linkage of years of Creation to the Seleucid era and then the Islamic era is to be found. The current erroneous linkage is explained.

II. List of systems of calculation used by the Samaritans

There are eight known Samaritan calculations of the relation between Years of Entry, Years of Creation, and Years of the Fānūta, on one hand, and absolute historical time, on the other, if the current calculation is counted.² They can be divided into an original; a recalculation not affecting reckoning of years of Creation after the start of the Fānūta, one form of which has a variant not affecting dates; some mistaken modifications; and various forms of ignorance.

The first reckoning, in ch. XI of the Asaṭīr, puts the crossing of the Jordan at the start of year 2797 Anno Mundi (hereinafter AM). See my book of 2024, pp. 177 bottom to 178. This is two years later than what A.F. thinks is right. This chapter of the Asaṭīr is not later than the early second century A.D. Multiple lines of proof of the dating of it are set out in my book.

The second reckoning is used by the Tūlādā. See my book of 2024, pp. 177 bottom to 178. Entry is on the first day of 2796 AM.

¹ **The author has no connection with the State of Israel.**

² The concept of the Time of Favour Rūuta ܐܢܘܬܐ (Aramaic definite feminine noun from the root ܐܢܘܐ) and the Time of Turning Away Fānūta ܐܢܘܬܐ (Aramaic definite feminine noun from the root ܐܢܘܐ) have been thoroughly described and this is not the place to rehearse common knowledge. The most accurate and informative study is Macdonald's book. The primary source is the Arabic Joshua book. On this, see my article *The Transmission of the Samaritan Joshua-Judges*. The form of the book in our hands is in Arabic, but this is a translation from Aramaic. What is relevant to my article here is set out at length in Part II of my book *A Samaritan Plan of Religious History*, but this article is intended to be adequate as it stands without supplement from elsewhere.

The third reckoning is used by a clumsy interpolator to the work of Abu 'l-Faḥ. (Hereinafter A.F. A convenient transcription of the name showing the actual pronunciation is Abu 'l-Fateḥ). The final editors of the Arabic Joshua book at the start of ch. 15 agree. Entry is at the start of 2795 AM. See my book again. The last year of Moses was a Jubilee year in their opinion. $[57 \times 49 + 1 = 2,794]$.

Part of the argument behind the dating is stated in the Arabic Joshua book at the start of ch. 15 in the interpolation after the figure 2,794 --- which is not the original figure. It says: "This date is demonstrable (or verifiable). The learned know it from the dates (plural) of the Flood". (Crane's translation is a jumble of words with a lot not in the text. Juynboll's has less words that are not in the text but is no better. He does not know the meaning of muṣaḥḥaḥ and guesses it is the same as ṣaḥīḥ. He knows what the common word tawārīkh means but gives it an impossible meaning). Part of the message is that the year and a bit while the eight were in the Ark is not to be counted, because Noah was 600 at the start and the end. These days we take the surface contradictions about the amount of time passed during the Flood as a signal by the editors that they're changing to a different calendar with a more exact length of year. The final editors of the Pentateuch were quite capable of packing two messages into one surprising verse. The first was a signal of a change of calendar with a more exact length of a year. The other was a signal that the time while the eight people and the animals were in the Ark was not experienced as time, because they were outside Creation. It says אַחַרְכֵּימֶנּוּ אֶת־הַיָּם וְאֶת־הַיַּבֵּשׁוֹת וְאֶת־הָאָרֶץ וְאֶת־הַיָּם וְאֶת־הַיַּבֵּשׁוֹת וְאֶת־הָאָרֶץ "The Lord closed up after him". All this is true but irrelevant to counting years of the world. A reminder of this reading of the Flood story is part of the message by the final editors of the Arabic Joshua book in their interpolation here. The other part is explained in the paragraph after next.

The explanation of how Shem could have been 100 at the start of the Flood and still 100 two years after the Flood is similar, but it was only Shem that was outside time for those two years. Time flowed for everyone else. As for what to make of this terse notice, the answer is easy. Shem was outside this world for those two years, learning from Melchizedek. They might have been thought to have been on the occulted top part of the top of Mt. Gerizim. ³

There is more explanation by someone pretending to be A.F. After repeating the total of 2,794 someone says firmly: "Anyone interested in this date is not to reject my adding up, since the Torah rounds fractions". These words go with the words in the final edition of the Arabic Joshua book just quoted. Noah and the other seven went into the Ark on the tenth of the second. Rain started on the 17th. The ground was dry in the sense of not being under water on the first of the first of the next year, and Noah moved or removed the hatch of the Ark. Time inside the Ark didn't start up again, since it says in Genesis VIII:13 that this was in the 601st year, that is, the year during which Noah was aged 600, and later on it says Noah was 600 when they came out of the Ark. ⁴ The ground was dried out by the 27th of the second, and they came out. The

³ Rabbinic tradition says Abraham studied in Shem's academy. It says firmly that Melchizedek is Shem. This fits in with the chronology of the MT, but not the Samaritan or LXX.

⁴ We learn from this that when it says God closed up after him, it doesn't mean closing the hatch, or doesn't only mean that, so it must mean taking them all out of time.

part years that someone has in mind is everything after the first month and 27 days of the second year, and the bit before they all went into the Ark on the tenth of the second in the first year.

The final editors of the Arabic Joshua book were not content with changing 2,796 to 2,794. They interpolate a sentence insisting it is right, and giving part of the thinking behind what they want accepted as proof. Someone pretending to be A.F. is not satisfied with giving the number and the sums behind it either, and gives the other part of the thinking behind it. Both of them show they know people need to be convinced. Neither says the date is traditional. Both arguments are dodgy. Why is a length of time in the Ark given in the Torah if it doesn't measure anything? The assertion about what the Torah does with part years is irrelevant. It is true that the Torah only gives whole years for the age of each person when their first son is born. It is true that this is how length of time is added up. The Flood came once. There's no first year of the next time to fit the second part year into, and no last year of the time before to fit the first bit of the first year into. The ten days of one year and the month and 27 days of the other vanish by one fallacy, and the time in between vanishes by another. Someone wanted Moses's last year to be a Jubilee year. I can't see why having a neat number for Moses's last year mattered enough to reject traditional knowledge of the year of entry, or mattered enough to lose knowledge of how to calculate sabbatical and Jubilee years, or mattered enough to forget that the Moslem conquest of Palestine had been in a Jubilee year. I think what A.F. wrote and what was in the Arabic Joshua book were both changed at the same time as whole pericopes in the book by A.F. were replaced by bad fictionalised history and fantasy. There is the same disregard for facts. The change is just as destructive. See my article *Samaritan History, Fiction, and Bad Fantasy*. The pushy tone here does not fit how A.F. addresses the reader. He knows how to think straight. The change of the figure for the year of Creation that A.F. wrote to nonsense could have happened at the same time.

I think the author of the Tūlāda turned the two calendar years of the Flood into one by not counting the time when they were all in the Ark and outside time, so that the length of a year less ten days was left. Near enough was good enough. Only one fallacy was needed.

I think the date of Entry into Canaan assumed in the Chain of High Priests, which is two years earlier than the one accepted by the final editors of the Arabic Joshua book and A.F. or an interpolator, comes from different exegesis of Genesis XI:10 on the birth of Arpachshad. I think the date of entry into Canaan was changed by not counting the length of the year the Flood started or the year it ended, then by not counting the two years from the start of the year the Flood started to the birth of Arpachshad, when Shem was outside this world, learning from Melchizedek. If so, then the dating depends on the fallacies used by the final editors of the Arabic Joshua book and the interpolator to the work of A.F. It must be secondary to secondary and very late. This dating too early by four years is used in the attachment to the Tūlāda, nine years before A.F. wrote. *The fallacious dating too early by two years must be older than the attachment.*

In the reckoning of years AM known to the real A.F. the year of the Hijrah starting on the 16th of July 622 AD started about three and a half months into year 5048 of Creation. Year 5048 AM started about three months into 622 AD. This means **4427 AM started about three**

months into 1 AD [5,048 take away 621 (sic) makes 4,427] and 1 AD started about nine months into 4426 AM. Year 1 of entry corresponds to year 2797 AM, so the difference is always 2,796. The year 4426 starting in late March of 1 BC is year 1630 of entry [4,426 take away 2,796 makes 1,630]. Then year 4427 AM starting in late March of 1 AD is year 1631 of entry. Then the year of entry starting in late March of 622 AD is year 1631 + 621 (sic) = 2252. The date of entry in the Asaṭīr is original. The other three supposed dates are alterations of this using a pair of fallacies. **The Samaritan religious year during which the Hijrah happened and which started in late March in 622 AD or about three and a half months into 5048 AM was year 2255 of entry.** [1,631 + 621 makes 2,252]. This was a 47th year. [46 x 49 = 2,254].

Some conversions to give perspective. The year 4427 AM started a few months into 1 AD [5,048 take away 621 (sic) makes 4,427]. Year 4426 AM started a few months into 1 BC. The start of **year of entry 2797 AM**, the year of crossing the Jordan, will be in late March of **1630 BC** [4,426 take away 2,796 (sic) = 1,630]. The start of the **Fānūta** was at the end of 3056 AM and the start of **3057 AM** [2,797 + 260 = 3,057] or **1370 BC** [1,630 take away 260 makes 1,370]. The **Exodus** is early April in **2837 AM** or **1670 BC**, forty years before entry into Canaan. **Creation** is in late March of **4426 BC**. [1,630 + 2,796 (sic) = 4,426]. The Jerusalem temple was completed 440 years (sic) from the Exodus in 3277 AM or 1230 BC. These are dates demanded by linking the Hijrah with a date a few months into 5028 AM, as A.F. does. (The interpolator did not touch this). A.F. must have known the exact conversion of the date of the Hijrah to the Seleucid calendar, and the traditional conversion of years AM to Seleucid years.

Here is linking to the dates of Eli and the first false sanctuary. Eli was 98 when he died, according to the Jewish record. This record says he had judged Israel for 40 years. That means he was 58 according to this record when he started to judge Israel. The Samaritan record says Eli put up his false sanctuary two years after Samson's death, seven years before the end of the Time of Favour. He was 50 when he decided he had been offended by the High Priest ^cAzzi. He would have been 51 when he put up the false sanctuary seven years before the end of the Time of Favour, so he would have been 58 when he started as illegitimate judge at the start of the first year of the Fānūta, so that his fifty-eighth birthday would have been during the first year of the Fānūta, and his ninety-eighth birthday would have been at the end of the fortieth year of the Fānūta and start of the forty-first, when he had been illegitimate judge for forty years. The Jewish scriptures say he had been judge. They don't say he had been High Priest. The recorded Samaritan and Jewish dates are parts of the same reckoning and fit together neatly.

Some linking to Jewish chronology. *If the start of building of the Jerusalem temple was 440 years after the Exodus, the figure in the original form of the Old Greek, then it was 400 years from the crossing of the Jordan. It has been shown that the crossing of the Jordan was in late March in 1630 BC (if we correct A.F. according to the Asaṭīr). This means it must have been built in the year running from late March in 1231 BC to late March in 1230 BC. This was 140 years from the start of the Fānūta or a hundred years from the end of the first false sanctuary. The false sanctuary at Shiloh was set up seven years before the fall of the Fānūta when Eli was 51 or 51 and a bit, and lasted till he was 98 and a bit, so it lasted 47 years, of which seven years were during the Time of Favour and forty during the Fānūta. It ended 340 years from the Exodus.*

[40 + 253 + 7 + 40 makes 340]. The start of building of the Jerusalem temple was in the fourth year of Solomon's reign. This means David died 137 years from the start of the Fānūta and his reign started 97 years from the start of the Fānūta. This makes the start of his reign 57 years from the death of Eli at the age of 98. The Jewish record says Samuel was very old when he died, but does not give a number. There is no number for Saul either. Both these omissions are suspicious, probably due to minimising Saul's reign in length and importance to fit a late dogma of a coming ruler descended from a fictionalised David and a massively fictionalised Solomon, but without tidying up. The Samaritan record gives Saul a lot of importance.

The MT adds forty years to the length of time from the Exodus to the start of work on the Jerusalem temple. This was probably to allow for the length of time assumed in the Jewish book of Judges, but it is still not enough. Both these numbers, 440 years and 480 years, assume a short period for the succession of judges without any pseudo-Deuteronomic account of falling away by the people taking up years between them. This means the ancestor of the Samaritan account (not the present form) is older than the extant Jewish record. See my article *The Transmission of the Samaritan Joshua-Judges*.

An observation compatible with what A.F. writes adds the seven bad years right at the end of the Time of Favour to the effective length of the Fānūta. The Hijrah in 5048 AM would be two thousand years and a bit after the start of the Fānūta at the start of 3055 AM if counting is to be from the start of 3048 AM seven years before the start of the Fānūta. This was entirely reasonable. This reckoning with seven more effective years is only extant in the second recension of A.F. Samson died nine years before the start of the Fānūta. After his death widespread ignorance of religion and deliberate flouting of the Torah as well as social degeneracy enabled Eli to get support for his false sanctuary with its counterfeit Ark of the Covenant at the wrong place, Shiloh. It is argued in my article *The Transmission of the Samaritan Joshua-Judges* that the ancestor of the extant Samaritan text was the original form of Joshua-Judges, before rewriting of both parts for Hasmonaeon ideology and using a counterfeit of Deuteronomic outlook to rewrite what is now Judges. In the extant Jewish text of Judges there is still a record of appalling social degeneracy after Samson's death, in agreement with the Samaritan record. It is not only the Samaritan record that says Eli was from the line of Ithamar, not Phineas. It can be worked out from the Jewish scriptures too, and the Amora'im are much exercised in trying to justify the flouting of the Torah. The story made up is clever but not an answer. If Eli went doubly against the Torah by making himself High Priest and in the wrong place there must have been a real High Priest at the right place, then and ever after.

The most likely time for the new reckoning of the shadow of the Fānūta as overlapping the last years of the Rūuta, the Time of Favour, was just after the end of Roman rule when Islamic rule restored sanity to the world. The frightfulness of the rule of Christian Rome is described in Part II of my book *A Samaritan Plan of Religious History*. The exactness of the year of the Hijrah as exactly two thousand years from the first gloom before the Fānūta with the setting up of the false sanctuary must have made an impression. This observation was not a separate way of reckoning, since no dates are changed: the datum that the Time of Favour lasted two hundred and sixty years was not denied. The first centuries of Moslem rule were a time of

recovery, though in Samaria it took three centuries to bring back full social order. See my article *Social Anomie*. Religion and culture flourished for centuries after that. The last part of the history by A.F. is not about his own time, but recognition of Samaritans by Muhammad with their legitimate place in the empire. With that he has said what is important.

The reckoning used by A.F. preserves the right linkage of Samaritan years of Creation with the date of the Hijrah on the 16th of July in 622 AD. It seems to have originally preserved the right linkage of years of Creation with Seleucid years. The *Asâṭir* preserves the right date for the start of counting for sabbatical and Jubilee years, whereas A.F. uses a number too early by two years and the *Tûlâda* has a number too early by one year. The authors of the last two would not have disagreed on conversion of years AM with Seleucid years after entry into Canaan. *With these two reference points absolute dates can be given for both years of Creation, and years of counting for sabbatical years, which are loosely called years of Entry.*

The fourth reckoning, found in the Hebrew pamphlet written in 1346 AD attached to the *Tûlâda*, might partly depend on misinterpretation of what the *Tûlâda* says about Alexander, with consequent guessing. Years of creation are five years too late. The traditional linkage of years of Creation to the Seleucid era was not known to the author. This is astonishing. The calculations showing this are set out below.

The fifth reckoning was done by a competent scholar in mid June 1703. He misread a table of sabbatical years and Jubilee years. Because of this, all numbers of years of Entry are too high by four years in relation to the reckoning in the *Tûlâda* or five years too high in relation to the reckoning known to A.F. Working backwards then gave numbers for years of Creation that were too high by the same amount. This is the same mistake as the third but happened independently.

Sixth come not a single calculation, but a profusion of them, piling one mistake on another. It is often impossible to work out how the mistakes happened. What matters is that for a long while there was no accepted reckoning, not even a wrong one.

The seventh calculation is an erroneous set of figures going back to arbitrary procedure in the listing of the High Priests in the *Comprehensive History* by Khaḍîr bin Ishâq or Fînâas ban Yêšâaq. This was completed by the author in 1865, and issued with an appendix ten years later. An early version must have been available in 1853. All years of Creation are lowered, due to following the extant defective list of High Priests in the mss. The author of *Chronicle Adler*, writing in 1900, copies but makes the mistakes worse. Most modern writers follow *Chronicle Adler*, without knowing where it comes from.

We finish with the eighth system of reckoning, the system of linkage between Samaritan and European dates currently in use in Samaritan publications. *It has been seen that A.F. puts the start of year 1633 of Entry in about late March in 1 AD. In modern calendars the correspondence of numbers of the years would mean the civil year 1640 of Entry started in late September (sic) in 1 AD and the religious year 1639 started in late March of 1 AD. This current*

reckoning comes from the mistaken figures for years of Entry in the calculations done in 1703, but with a complication. The complication is that civil years are given as years of entry and not years of Creation. The reason for counting both religious years and civil years from entry is that the conversion of years of Creation to Seleucid years was lost soon after A.F. wrote. The conversion known to A.F. is recovered in this article. The conversions assumed by the Tūlāda and Asaṭīr are the same.

There is some rough correction of the dates in the extant mss. of A.F. In what follows the references are to the page and line nos. of Vilmar's edition. At 178:9 -- 12 the author, A.F., gives the correspondence of years of Creation with 756 Anno Hegirae (hereinafter AH), the year of finishing the book. This is 1355 AD. This date with its synchronisation was meant to be the key to the chronology used throughout the book. At this point the author's original date has been replaced. The way it was done was so clumsy there can be no doubt as to what has gone wrong. The figure of 756, the year of the Islamic calendar in which the book was finished, has been added to 5047, changing the year of composition to 5803 AM. But 756 Islamic years are not equal to 756 solar years, as everyone knows. Only ms. C has this reading, the original corruption. This change must be earlier than the date of ms. C, 1523 AD, since it is shown below that a secondary corruption derived from this first corruption can be dated to 1518 AD, so the original mistake can be pushed back to 1500 AD or a bit before. Then the false date of 5,803 years from Creation was corrupted further at a later stage of copying. In ms. D, written in 1545 AD, the erroneous figure as now seen in ms. C has been changed to the erroneous figure of the year 5945 AM, with the addition of another 141 years. My guess is that someone saw that 5,803 years from Creation could not be the date of composition, and thought it must be the date of copying of the ms. in which this date had first been set down. If it had been wrongly thought that the figure 5047 apparently given by AF was meant to synchronise with the Hijrah, the year starting 5,803 years from Creation would have been thought to have been 756 (5,803 take away 5,047) solar years from the Hijrah, what we would call 1378 AD. This would have been thought to be only 23 years from the composition of the book in 1355 AD. Corruption so early would have been thought impossible, so it could have been assumed the date was meant to be the date of writing out of an authoritative ms., perhaps by AF himself, but certainly by someone copying the autograph. The scribe would then have felt free to change the date that he thought to be the record of the date of copying of the ancestral exemplar to the current date, the year of his copying of the book, which would have been the year starting 5,944 years (5,803 + 141) from Creation = the year 5945 AM = 897 years (5,944 take away 5047) after 621 AD = 1518 AD. This is only 27 years before the copying of ms. D. This secondary corruption is in all later mss.

III. The two secondary synchronisations given by A.F.

The original main synchronisation with the date of the book being lost, we have to rely on inference from the two secondary synchronisations by A.F., one with Alexander and one with Muhammad. The second secondary synchronisation, with Muhammad, is given in five separate places. Clearly A.F. must have believed that if anything could go wrong in the process of copying, it would, and he allowed for it.

First secondary synchronisation. A.F. 84:1--5. From Creation till the end of the days of the High Priest Izqiyya is said to be 4,100 years. From the start of the Fānūta till this date is said to be 1,046 years. This means A.F. puts entry into Canaan in the middle of 2795 AM, which puts the start of the Fānūta at the end of 3054 AM and the start of 3055 AM. His officiate is said to have lasted 21 years. Then A.F. says that in his days came Alexander the Macedonian. Descriptive but not narrative material about Izqiyya then continues till the mention of his death at 93:14--15. It says at 92:10--11 that Izqiyya worried about the fate of the Samaritans under the next ruler. The length of time from the death of Alexander till the death of Izqiyya is not given. This vagueness is out of character for A.F. and needs to be looked into. Alexander died on 11/6/323 BC, about three months after the end of the Samaritan year in late March. Following normal practice, A.F. does not count an incomplete last year of office here, which means this High Priest died during 4101 AM. A.F. would have known the date of 4100 AM by tradition. The end of 4100 AM or start of 4101 AM corresponds to late March of 325 BC. [The year starting in late March of 1 AD is 4427 AM. See pp. 3 – 4. So the start of 4100 AM will be in late March of 327 and it will end in late March of 326 BC]. All that is meant is that he conquered Palestine while Izqiyya was officiating and the Samaritans benefited from his rule. There is a record of his endowment of the sacred place. See my book of 2024, p.109. The information about the date of Alexander according to years of Creation is still useful, even if it only gives an approximation of the correspondence for conversion.

The main secondary synchronisation. This date is important to A.F. and he is precise this time. He gives it five times over. (a) The main statement given in his Foreword has been corrupted. See below. (b) At A.F. 172:16--18 it is said that from the start of the Fanūta till the coming of Muḥammad is 1,993 years, and from Creation 5,047 years. **This means in the year 5048 AM which works out at year 2254 of Entry.** [5,048 take away 2,795 makes 2,253. Then add 1 because 2795 AM was year 1 of Entry]. This is said to have been at the end of the officiate of Elaāzar, which lasted 25 years. (c) At 175:13 the coming of Muḥammad is said to have been 5,047 years from Creation. This would mean during 5048 AM. (d) At 176:12 the coming of Muḥammad is said to have been 1,993 years from the start of the Fānūta. [The Fānūta started when 260 full years had passed since Entry, at the start of year 261 of Entry, which was the start of year 5055 AM according to A.F. This means 1,993 whole years and about three and a half months had passed]. (e) At 178:9 the date for the coming of Muḥammad is given again. In all the extant mss., this is said to have been in the 12th year of the officiate of Elaāzar, contradicting what was said at 172:16--18 and introducing an error of 13 years. Whoever first witlessly changed the date of composition of the book just after this statement, at 178:9--12, made this change as well, putting the date of the “coming” of Muhammad thirteen years too early in relation to the sequence of High Priests, according to some theory of his own.

The Moslems were seen as the saviour of the Samaritans, along with all other kinds of Palestinians, whether Pagans, Gnostics, Jews, or Christians with the wrong label. It is highly remarkable that this figure should have got lost by 1500 AD or a bit earlier, less than a hundred and fifty years from the book’s composition, but there was very early corruption to the text. See my book, at the start of Part VII. It is just as remarkable that the figure was not well known when the attachment to the Tūlāda was written, in 1346, nine years before A.F. wrote.

IV. The attested types of erroneous synchronisation

(a) First set of examples of erroneous synchronisation. One item.

As said, a pamphlet stands in the mss. before the older Tūlāda. The author tries to be thorough but is confused. He does not use the solid datum in the Tūlāda for the year of Creation when the Time of Favour ended, from which the year when it started could have been worked out. He writes in the third month of the Islamic year 747 corresponding to the fourth month of the Seleucid year, which is July. [This would be 1346 AD, only nine years before AF wrote his history]. This year is said to correspond to 5778 AM which is said to correspond to year 714 Persian, meaning in the Yezdegerd Era, which started in 632 AD. That means 5778 AM started in about late March in 1346 AD according to this author. This would make the year starting in late March in 1 AD correspond to 4433 AM. [5,778 take away 1,345 (sic) = 4,433]. A.F. makes it 4427 AM. The number for the year of Creation is 6 years too low. This ignorance is astonishing. There is more that is wrong. The year of writing is said to be 2,984 years since starting the observing of shemittot. This means he must put the crossing of the Jordan two years earlier than in the Tūlāda, and one year earlier than A.F. does, at the start of 2794 AM. [2,794 + 2,984 = 5,778]. The Chain of High Priests puts the death of the High Priest ^cAzzi at the end of 3053 AM. What is meant is that he died a few months into 3054 AM, after the start of the Fānūta at the start of the year. This would put the crossing of the Jordan at the start of 2794 AM, in agreement with this attachment. The number in the Chain of High Priests could have been used by the author of the attachment, or it might come from his own faulty arithmetic. The number in the Chain of High Priests seems to have been arrived at by adding up years of High Priests, since it is attached to the mention of ^cAzzi and is given as the date of his death. The date in the Tūlāda is presented as the traditional date of the fall of the Fānūta, even though it sits in a list of High Priests with the lengths of their officiate. This is not the whole story. This mistaken numbering of the year of Entry could not have been used to arrive at the mistaken numbering of the year of Creation of the year of writing, since the two mistakes contradict each other. Not knowing the right year of Creation of the time of writing is astonishing. I think the reason for the mistake of having a number 6 years too low for the current year AM is that he has read too much into what is said in the Tūlāda about Alexander coming during the time of Izqiyya on p. 85. Nine years later, A.F. does his best to stop these mistakes from happening.

The author calls his pamphlet a māshni [mšnh], meaning supplement. [A. D. Crown says it means a copying and thinks it refers to everything that follows. He has mechanically looked the word up in a dictionary and not thought. He has not seen the author's own description of his work, or not taken notice. He does not know Hebrew well enough to tell the difference between the proper Hebrew in the supplement and the Hebrew badly contaminated by Aramaic in the Tūlāda. In general I don't bother mentioning Crown's blunders due to ignorance of Hebrew, lack of critical thinking, carelessness, and unacknowledged invention, because it would be a waste of the reader's time. I only mention this one because it might deceive some people]. Later readers have regarded the attachment as part of the book, without stopping to think that the attachment and the book were written by two different authors. There are parts of the content of the attachment that are not original to the author but traditional

knowledge, of which the most important is the correct figure for the position of the Mountain. In later times this attachment was the most convenient reference for this kind of information.

(b) Second set of examples of erroneous synchronisation. Three items

(1). Colophon of Samaritan ms. IX part 2 in the Rylands Library at Manchester, translation of the Asâṭir. The scribe is the renowned Musallam bin Marjân Dinfi. The date is given as Šafar 1115 AH [Anno Hegirae] (which month started in mid June 1703) along with June 2016 Greek [June 1703 AD] along with 6141 AM along with 3441 of Entry. This would make the year of crossing the Jordan or year 1 of Entry 2700 AM. I think this is a mistake for 2800, which would still be wrong. Calculating now from the date for Muhammad in 622 AD (which Musallam did not do). This was in 5048 AM according to A.F., which was year 2254 of Entry if the crossing of the Jordan at the start of year 2795 AM was at the start of year 1 of Entry. [The difference between 5,048 and 2,795 is 2,253. Then $1 + 2,253 = 2,254$]. From 622 AD till 1703 AD is 1,081 years. Then $5,048 + 1,081 = 6,129$. So 6129 AM starts in late March of 1703 AD. This year 6129 AM corresponds to year 3334 of entry. Then 1703 AD will start about three months into year 3333 of Entry. [Checking. If year 5048 AM which is year 2254 of Entry starts in 622 AD, then 4427 AM starts in 1 BC. [5,048 take away 622 makes 4,427]. It follows that the start of 1 AD will be a few months into year 4428 AM. This is right. More checking. If year 4427 AM started in late March in 1 BC, then 6141 AM started in late March in 1714 AD. [6,141 take away 4,427 makes 1,714]. Musallam puts the start of 6141 AM in 1703. The year AM is too low by 11 years. Now we see a worse mistake. Musallam thinks this is the year before a Jubilee year. He is wrong. Year 3442 of Entry was not a Jubilee. [$70 \times 49 = 3,430$]. This also makes Entry only 2,700 years after Creation, or 94 years too early in relation to what A.F. makes it! We start with the assumption that although Musallam could make mistakes in arithmetic, he would not be wrong on a point of fact. I have had a look at the photograph of the page in the catalogue. The dates are written in Hebrew letters. For 3441 he has written gimel then the word thousand (alf) in full and then the letters qof shin mem alef. The sequence qof shin is anomalous. For 300, shin would be written and for 400, tav. The words of the two lines with the two dates are exactly underneath each other from start to finish. The letters qof shin mem alef are written exactly under the letters qof mem alef of the date from Creation. The shin was mistakenly copied from the line above along with the qof from above. As said, the sequence qof shin is impossible, so shin alone must be meant. The mem was copied correctly from the line above. It might be thought that Musallam forgot to change the alef in the top line to zayin, but this is not a mistake, as will be seen from the next example. A difference of 2,800 and not 2,794 years from Creation till Entry really is what was intended. This would make all years of Entry 6 years too high in relation to what A.F. thinks. The figure for years of Entry is 106 years too high. The 100 years is probably a mistake in arithmetic, so he puts the number of all years of Entry 6 years too high.

The origin of the addition of 6 years to years of Entry is this. Tables of the Ishbæn Qashta are converted to tables of years of Creation by adding 2,800 ($2,794 + 6$) and converted to tables of years of Entry by adding 6. If you start by looking at what you think is the current year of Entry in the tables of Ishbæn Qashta with their correspondences to years of Creation, and if it is thought that the I.Q. column is a Year of Entry column, it will seem that the rule is that the

difference between years of Creation and years of Entry ought to be 2,800 years. If this supposed rule is then used in conversions, and if years of Entry are the base, all years of Creation will come out 6 years more than they ought to be. The consequence will be that the starting point of Years of Entry will be 2,800 instead of 2,794 years from Creation. As to how anyone might think this to be right, the answer is simple --- though Musallam must have been badly distracted. The appendix standing before the Tūlāda has been misread at 4a:36-39 and then 3b:10. [This is Florentin's numbering. Neubauer p. 428 translation and p. 394 text and p. 428 translation; p. 391 text and p. 425 translation]. Somehow it has been thought that words that mean seven years on the western side of the Jordan, mean the eastern side of the Jordan. (In the language of the Torah, the expression "The Trans-Jordan" or "the other side of the Jordan" means the other side from the reference point of the situation of the utterance. It can mean the east side or the west side. If what is meant is not clear from the context, then "on the east" or "on the west" is added. At 4a:36--39 it says there was a delay of six years "while the Israelites were across the Jordan on the west" before doing the astronomical observations and calculations needed for the calculation of the tables or almanac [now called the *ܝܫܒܥܢܩܫܬܐ* Ishbæen Qashṭa in Aramaic, meaning the correct reckoning]. This is reasonable, because observations were not needed before Year 6, when it was time to prepare for Year 7, the first sabbatical year. It says elsewhere, not here, that the year when the observations were made was not year one of counting of shemittot but year six. Here it says that to convert years of the almanac to years of Entry you add six. It is said at 3b:10 that the knowledge of astronomy needed for this purpose was revealed in the year 2794 of Creation, that is, the year leading up to the crossing of the Jordan. Unbelievable as it might seem, someone has read the first passage, 4a:36-39, as meaning there was a delay of six years before crossing the Jordan. The implication would be that Entry was at the end of 2,800 years, not 2,794. For a long while I looked for some other explanation, because it was hard to suppose anyone could have been so insensitive to the text or ignorant. There plainly is the word "westwards" [yamma]. Then I saw that Adolf Neubauer had made exactly this mistake in his translation into French. As for what he had done with the word "westwards", he had simply declined to take notice of it. I had already seen that Neubauer's translation is inaccurate in many places, where the syntax of the Hebrew had been too hard for him. Here it was syntax and vocabulary and information from common knowledge that were all too hard at once. [There is a bad misprint in Neubauer's Hebrew text, which has "interior" or "wilderness" (mdbr) instead of "Jordan" (yrdn). The French translation, bad as it is, depends on the correct Hebrew text]. Florentin gets the syntax right, as would be expected, and understands from the context that the western side of the Jordan must be meant. He still does not see the relevance of the word "westwards" as being a necessary definer of the ambiguous phrase "across the Jordan". Accordingly, he wrongly explains it as meaning the Israelites were concentrated on the westward side of what we call the Cis-Jordan, the Mediterranean side, but could not enter the eastern part of the western side. If Neubauer could make a careless blunder here, and even the meticulous Florentin could be a bit off track, then so could someone else. So here is the explanation of the wrong dating of years of Entry by 6 years: misreading of the appendix to the Tūlāda, in more than one respect. The first part of this ms., the Kitāb at-Ṭubâkh, was written out by four members of the Dinfi family, including Musallam, between 1692 and 1711. The calculation at the end of this ms., after the second part, would have been widely known. Ms. Manchester IX is carefully and elaborately written in both parts. The text of the Ṭubâkh (the first part of the ms.) has been

copied from one very good ms. with collation against at least one other very good ms. with consequent improvements. There is only one extant older ms. of the Ṭubâkh. The text of the Asâtîr in the commentary copied in the same volume as the second part is superior to most mss. of the book. The whole volume seems to have been intended as two model exemplars. This means the correspondences of dates in the colophon would have been thought to be accurate. If the learned Musallam could pile mistakes up, and then not think to divide the supposed year of Entry by 49 to see if it worked, anyone could get their sums wrong and get confused. Anyone could have looked at A.F., but no-one did. This is a good example of the need to look out for late invention and sift it out from real tradition.

(2) Rylands Library at Manchester University. Samaritan ms. XXII. Astronomical calendar, written by Marjân bin Ibrâhim, Musallam bin Marjân, and ʿAbdullâh bin Yûsuf. The ms. was completed on the 9th of Dhul-Hijja 1124 which is the 25th December of the Greek year 2025 [1712 AD] which is said to be in the tenth month of a Jubilee Year. What must be meant is that this is year 3333 of Entry. [$68 \times 49 + 1 = 3,333$]. If $1712 = 3333$ of Entry, then late March in 1 AD = 3333 less $1711 = 1622$ of Entry. This is 11 years too low in relation to the reckoning used by A.F. or 10 years too low in relation to the reckoning used in the Tûlâda. Years have been deducted to try to correct the error in the second set of tables written and used by Musallam but they have been deducted from a figure that was accurate, from the first set of tables used by Musallam! *Confusion is complete.*

(3) Improvement but not success. Colophon of Samaritan ms. 171 in the Rylands Library at Manchester University. Kitâb aṭ-Ṭubâkh, written mostly by Marjân bin Asʿad Dinfi. Colophon. Finished on the 8th of the 7th of the religious year near the start of year 3521 of Entry which is said to be in Dhu ʿl-Hijja 1300 AH [which month started on the 2nd October 1883]. (I don't see how he can say the date is near the start of the year, unless the explanation at the top of p. 15 is right). This means year 3521 of Entry was 6315 AM if the date of Entry used by A.F. is used. [$2,794$ (sic) + $3,521 = 6,315$]. This would make late March in 1 AD correspond to the start of year 1639 of Entry. [$3,521$ take away $1,882$ makes $1,639$]. This is too high by six years.

(c) Third set of examples of erroneous synchronisation. Six items.

Surprising as it might be, in the mid 19th century calculations start to be made from the lists of High Priests in the Tûlâda without realising that all the extant mss. are defective. There are two big omissions of High Priests between the time of Hadrian and the time of Constantine. These might be mistakes, but it seems unlikely. My suggestion is that these two blocks of High Priests were Dositheans, and they were removed at a time when this was still remembered. Apparently no-one thought to correct the defect by looking at the listing of High Priests by A.F. from an undamaged list.

(1). The early mss. of the history by A.F. preserve his original dating of Muḥammad. Ms. S has a note on p. 310 in modern handwriting that would fit the late 19th century saying the correct figure for years from Fânûta to Muḥammad ought to be 1,884 instead of the figure of 1,993 in the text. This would make the Hijrah too early by 109 years.

(2). Ms. A of A.F., written in 1857, gives the original date, and in the body of the text, not in the margin, an alternative of 4,896 years from Creation to Muḥammad (instead of 5,047). This makes the Hijrah too early by 5,047 take away 4,896 = 151 years. All mss. of the work of A.F. after this date depart from the author's intention. Mss. P₁L₁ (both 1863) L₂Y (both 1868) N (between 1865 and 1880) M (late 19th c.) and L₃ (between 1900 and 1905) have the original date of 1,993 years from Fānūta till Muḥammad then an alternative of 1,884 years from the start of the Fānūta till Muḥammad then the original 5,047 years from Creation to Muḥammad. Ms J (1908) has only these new figures in the text, without any hint to the reader that they are not what the author wrote.

(3). These new dates are in fact derived from early calculations for the book often known as the Comprehensive History by Khaḍīr bin Ishāq or Fināas ban Yēṣāaq, completed in 1875. The Hijrah is set in 4893 AM [starting 4,892 whole years since creation] said to be year 3099 of Entry [starting 3,098 whole years since Entry] said to be 1838 years since the first year of the Fānūta, which is known to correspond to year 261 of Entry or 2055 AM. This correctly makes 2,794 years from Creation to Entry. If what is meant is that the Hijrah is in the year starting 4893 years from Creation, this is too early by 5,047 take away 4,893 = 154 years. These figures can be explained in part by the loss of 135 years in the listing of High Priests in the extant mss. of the Tūlāda. Khaḍīr has added up the years of the High Priests from the death of Alexander to the Hijrah without realising that all mss. available to him were seriously wrong. I can't work out how Khaḍīr managed to delete another 19 years.

(4) Colophon of Samaritan ms. 288 in the Rylands Library at Manchester. Tūlāda. 1276 AH is said to correspond to 1860 AD (in the margin) or 1861 AD (in the margin) and correspond to 6177 AM. This would make 1 AD correspond to 4317 AM or 4318 AM. [6,177 take away 1,860 makes 4,317]. The year AM is too early by either 110 or 109 years. [4,427 take away 4,317 = 110]. New calculations are going on. They seem to derive from the ones being done at the time for the Comprehensive History.

(5). Colophon of Samaritan ms. 258 in the Rylands Library at Manchester. A Hebrew chronicle derived from the Comprehensive History. 10th month of 1326 AH = 6227 AM = 3433 of entry = October 1908 AD. This would make late March in 1 AD = 6227 less 1907 = the start of 4320 AM. [6,227 take away 1,906 makes 4,311]. This is too low by 107 years. The period till Entry has been calculated from the figure 6227, with the answer coming out as 2,794 which must have been expected.

(6). A note in the margin of many of the late mss. of AF says the Tūlāda makes it 4,869 years from Creation to Muhammad. This is too early by 178 years. The explanation is that there is a long omission in the listing of High Priests in the extant mss. of the Tūlāda, as has been said, and someone has noticed and tried to do some repair, but without knowing how.

(d) Fourth set of examples of erroneous synchronisation

The previous chronology, based on misuse of defective lists of High Priests, was abandoned. The replacement dating is better but still not right. First attestation is in 1924.

(1). Rylands Library at Manchester University, Samaritan ms. 307. Calendar. Year 6376 of Creation is said to be 3570 of Entry, which is said to be 1356 AH [1937]. It is said to be a second year of a shemittah set. This is wrong. Checking years of Creation. If late March 1937 AD is the start of 6376 AM, then late March 1 AD is 6,376 take away 1,936 = the start of 4440 AM. [6,376 take away 1,936 makes 4,440]. This is 7 years too high. Checking what are said to be years of Entry and years of shemittah. $73 \times 49 = 3,557$, so year 3570 is year $73 \times 49 + 7 + 6$, which is the year before a shemittah year or seventh year, so the figure in the calendar is 3 years late. The correct difference between years of Creation and years of Entry according to A.F. is 2,794. This calendar makes it 2,800, a mistake of six years. The calendar for the year before (Manchester 306) says that year, starting in late 1936 AD, is year 6375 of Entry. This would make the year of entry starting in late March in 1 AD = 4440, the same mistake. It says it was a shemittah year, which it was not. *All system has been lost*. The first of the calendars in the Manchester collection is for the year starting in late 1924 AD (Manchester 295). The last is for 1939 (Manchester 308). The same chronology is assumed in all of them, but I have chosen the one for 1937 because the figures are specially detailed.

(2). Freie Universität Berlin, ms. 16. Liturgy. Dated by the Islamic and the Jewish calendars to a date equivalent to April 1962 AD. This would correspond to year 3594 of Entry if the reckoning used by A.F. were followed. [$1,633 + 1,961$ (sic) = 3,594]. The year of Entry is said to be 3602. This is 8 years too high in relation to the reckoning used by A.F. This looks like a mistake, though it is hard to see how anyone could make such a mistake.

(3) The current synchronisation in Samaritan calendars. *All dates of years of Entry are too high by 7 years in relation to the reckoning used by the interpolator to A.F., which means too high by 5 years in relation to the Asaṭīr and what would have been accepted by the real A.F. Linkage with years of Creation is impossible*. The origin of this reckoning is the page of calculations by Musallam bin Murjān in 1703 AD, and the addition of six years by misreading the Tūlāda. See pp. 10 middle to 12 middle. Here's how the modern numbering has been invented. The seventh year in the dates of calendars was conjured up by describing the calendar using the numbering of the civil year starting six months after the start of the religious year. The loss of knowledge is obscured by counting from entry, an entirely modern practice, and then this next change in practice, giving the number for the civil year, helps obscure the loss of knowledge even further. The knowledge of how to convert years of Creation to Seleucid or Christian years was thought to be lost because the main correspondence given by A.F. had been corrupted. No-one thought to use the correspondence with the Hijrah given by A.F. Here's how the modern numbering system works. The numbering of the year in the calendar changes at the start of the seventh month, for a new civil year. If such civil years are projected back to the year of entry, then it might be thought that civil year 2 started at the start of the seventh month of the first year of entry. The first six months of the year would have been thought to be in an incomplete civil year. A civil year starting in the seventh month seems to be presupposed in the colophon of a manuscript of the Kitāb aṭ-Ṭubākh mentioned on p. 12. What is done can only be seen by looking carefully at the calendars. The information on different Samaritan websites is useless. Never try to rely on Benyamim Tsedaka for explanation of a principle or statement of an exact datum. He

actually says the same year changes its number halfway through the twelve months. He says entry into Canaan was in the sixth month. By this he means the seventh month I suppose. To say this, he must be counting from the start of the civil year and confusing it with the religious year. I can't work out the reason for setting calendars out this way. A calendar showing the numbering of civil years might be needed for dating marriage certificates.

V. The Jubilee year

The Jubilee year has the same start and finish as years of Creation. The day after the Day of Atonement in the seventh month of the forty-ninth year the High Priest and King together send out heralds to all countries to announce the coming of the Jubilee year over the next six months. Ghazâl uses the word bashâ'ir in the plural for the announcements. It does not refer to the content but the numerous acts of announcement in different places. (The Hebrew and Aramaic cognates of this word are behind the Greek word euangēlion, which was meant to mean heralding, not good news). What Ghazâl says about the start and end in his Commentary on Leviticus is confirmed by the Arabic Joshua book at the start of ch. 15. "The cloud was lifted up on the first day of the first month of the first shemittah of the Jubilee right at the start of the entry of the Israelites etc.". Entry was on the first day of the first month of the first year. The start of the astronomical observations needed was in the sixth year.

The Jubilee year is the fiftieth year. It corresponds to the first year of the first shemittah period of the next period of forty-nine and fifty years.⁵

⁵ Information about the Samaritan halachah of the Jubilee year has never been published. I used the Leviticus volume of the massive collection of old commentary on the Torah entitled *Kâshif al Ghayâhib* by Ghazâl bin Abi 's-Surûr. All printed references to this commentary are to ms. Petermann 1:4c in the National Library in Berlin. It is Pohl's judgment that the text is not very good and not copied well. No-one knew any better because no-one asked me where to look. Weigelt does not mention the accurate ms. in his survey of commentaries because he did not know about it because he has never contacted me because he was ordered not to. This is the great drawback to obeying others that think they are important enough to declare people unkosher. I despise weakness. In his survey of mss. of commentaries on the Torah presented at a conference of the Société d'Etudes samaritaines in 1988 and published in 1991 Heinz Pohl says it is the Numbers volume. He was wrong because he had been prevented from contacting me. He had deliberately been given a false address for me, so he couldn't tell me his new address. On the long sordid story of giving out false addresses for me over years and years, see my blurb on the Academia website before my article *La Purification de Jésus*. The Société d'Etudes samaritaines was no help because they had been given orders. I only got Pohl's new address when I ran into him in Europe not long before he died. I used ms. O. Nova 517 in Uppsala University Library, which is copied carefully from a ms. with the author's original wording. It is the Leviticus volume. The Jubilee Year, the fiftieth year, is announced in the liturgy on the first of the seventh of the religious year, which is the start of the civil year in about late September, in the forty-ninth year, and then publicly announced by the blowing of the shofar in a more elaborate way than usual on the Day of Atonement on the tenth of the seventh. This allows six months for emissaries or heralds to go out into all countries after the Day of Atonement in the forty-ninth year to officially announce the approach of the fiftieth year, the Jubilee, which corresponds to the religious year starting on the first of the first. The shofar is blown in a special way on the Day of Atonement in the fiftieth year. The Jewish authoritative books, both Karaite and Rabbanite, are useless. There is no mention in them of any formal announcement at the start of the forty-ninth year or special blowing of the shofar on the Day of Atonement that year, only the announcement and blowing

VI. Conclusions and observations

There will be some repetition of what has gone before, but it will be connected with new observations.

There are three old Samaritan traditions of correspondence between the years of counting of sabbatical and Jubilee years and foreign eras. The first is assumed by the Asâṭir, in the early second century A.D. or a bit earlier. The second is assumed by the Tūlāda. Entry is one year earlier than the number in the Asaṭīr. A.F. in 1355 makes the date of Entry into Canaan one year earlier than in the Tūlāda. This made the year of the Hijrah a forty-ninth year. This seems to be artificial new reckoning. Both A.F. and the Arabic Joshua book in ch. 15 cryptically mention the need to understand what is said about the chronology of the Flood. What is meant was explained earlier in this article. The need to assert that the reckoning is right, with cryptic specification of one half of the double fallacy, is evidence that it is a departure from tradition. The antiquity of the reckoning in the Asaṭīr is confirmed.

A.F. restored the tradition of the synchronisation of years of Creation with absolute years or Islamic and Seleucid years. ⁶ He did not know the tradition of synchronisation of years of creation with years of Entry, or more likely did not believe in it. He puts the date of crossing the Jordan two years earlier than the Asâṭir does. The primary reference point he gives the reader is the exact date of completion of his book according to both years of Creation and the Islamic Era, and he also gives the figure for conversion to years of Entry. He also tries to give a loose correlation with the year of death of Alexander. He correlates years of Creation with the Islamic era in five places. His caution was well justified. Before 1500 AD his primary statement of correlation, between the year of writing according to the Islamic Era and the same year according to years of Creation, was lost by an act of stupidity. So was one instance of the four statements of correlation with the start of Islamic rule. The tradition of the connection of a Jubilee year with the end of Byzantine rule must have been lost even before that. After that, as early as 1703 AD, if not earlier, a second mistake was made. The formula converting years of the almanac [*אשבת קשטא* Ishbæn Qasṭa] to years of Entry by adding 6 was lost by misreading the attachment to the Tūlāda, even though the explanation at the relevant point is clear. Year 1 of Entry was thus put 6 years too late in relation to years of Creation. The numbering of years of Creation was not affected. Adolf Neubauer made the same blunder. The

of the shofar on the Day of Atonement of the fiftieth year. There is no mention of sending heralds out. This silence is not from traditional knowledge. **There is no Jewish tradition at all, not on a single detail.** They aren't even sure whether Jubilee years are forty-nine or fifty years apart. In the Mishnah the Tanna'im reject the information that is partly right and make the wrong decision. The Amora'im guess. What ever happened to the much-vaunted Oral Torah here? The Karaites are more honest and admit that all tradition is lost. We have no information at all about Jewish practice from before the anti-eschatological Seder 'Olam Rabba, composed in about 140 or 145 AD, soon after the ending of the second war with Rome.

⁶ This is not the only place where A.F. restores correct information. For example, he restores the correct chronology of the Kings of the Time of Favour [called the Judges in the Jewish tradition] that had been lost in vulgar mss. of the Arabic Joshua. He also restores the names that had been lost, though only to some extent. See my article *The Transmission of the Samaritan Joshua-Judges*.

attachment to the Tūlāda was already out by six years in the correspondence of years of Creation to Seleucid or Islamic years. An observation compatible with A.F. makes the shadow of the onset of the Fānūta seven years earlier, but without changing the real length of the Time of Favour, which is still two hundred and sixty years. This makes the effective length of the Fānūta exactly two thousand years if you count from the setting up of the false sanctuary at Shiloh by Eli. This was two years after Samson's death and the start of general corruption of behaviour. Of course, this observation would be compatible with the Asâtir and Tūlāda if the false sanctuary were thought to have been set up one year after Samson's death. The original narrative would allow this and would read more naturally that way. The counterfeit Ark from Shiloh ended up in Jerusalem. Holding it was used as an excuse for building a temple. Contrary to popular belief, this was not authorised by any prophecy by the prophet Nathan but only in his own words and only ambiguously. The Christian Church claimed to have taken over the status of the Jerusalem temple, and claimed legitimation from the scriptures associated with it. In denial of Numbers XII and the last verses of Deuteronomy, these books were put at the level of the Torah. In practice the Church put them higher, because it needed them to try to prove the claims it made about Jesus. The Christian Church then used the power of the Roman empire to massacre Samaritans in Palestine and other countries, and at the same time make it economically impossible for any Samaritan to survive anywhere. This lasted till the Moslem conquest. In the lands remaining under Roman rule, it still kept up after then. This exact timing of two thousand years from the first cause of centuries of murder and oppression and attack on the religion adds a second implication that the coming of Moslem rule was Providential. *The attack on the religion had started two thousand years before. The first false sanctuary at Shiloh was used to try to forget about the real sacred place, and it opened the way for the second false sanctuary in Jerusalem, even providing a counterfeit Ark of the Covenant. The Christian Church took over the ideology of the builders of the second false sanctuary and claimed both its authority and the authority of the writings connected with it, the Jewish scriptures.*

The author of the attachment to the Tūlāda wrote in 1346 AD, nine years before AF. He did not know the correspondence to the Seleucid Era or the Islamic Era known to A.F. The purpose of the attachment was to systematically record necessary items of traditional data that might have got lost. It is well organised and well presented. The author knows the figure for the exact position of the mountain down to the last second of degree. He understands that although the first entry in a list of sabbatical years will be for year 7 of Entry, counting started from year 1 of Entry, and warns the reader against reading year 1 of the tables as year 1 of Entry. It is therefore remarkable that the author did not have the tradition of the linkage of years of Creation to Seleucid years and Islamic years, even though it was known to A.F., writing nine years later. He makes all dates by year of Creation too low because he makes the year of Entry too early, going by the Chain of High Priests instead of the Tūlāda.

After the time of A.F., there is a string of guesses about dating for centuries on end, all due to loss of tradition, with consequent understandable mistakes as well as a couple of stupid mistakes. In the twentieth century there was improvement, but it was not complete. Years of Entry were made too late by 6 years. The page of calculations by Musallam bin Marjān could have been used. A.F. gave an answer but it would have been seen that he disagrees with the

Tūlāda on the year of crossing the Jordan. Besides this, it would not have been understood how the numbers in the mss. of his history for years of Creation had become corrupted in some places. *It is now impossible for the Samaritans to give dates by years of Creation. The knowledge was lost 450 years ago when the correspondence given by A.F. was wiped out. If they ever get round to reading this article, they can restore the formula for conversion. They won't need to choose between the date of entry into Canaan given by the Asaṭīr or the Tūlāda or A.F., and they won't need to decide how to treat the year and a bit when the eight were in the Ark.*

The unbelievable but inevitable conclusion is that there has been no precise Samaritan tradition of the linkage of years of Creation and years of Entry to foreign years since some time round before 1500 A.D., when the primary synchronisation with the Islamic Era given by A.F. in the foreword to his book was wiped out, and three of the rest of the synchronisations were ignored and one wiped out. The loss of knowledge started well before then, since the attachment to the Tūlāda made years of Creation too low, and this was a writing carefully composed. Such loss of knowledge is inexplicable. Anyone could have looked at what A.F. wrote, but no-one did. Even the chronology known to A.F. is later than the Asaṭīr and artificial. Note that although that change affected the linkage of years of Entry to Seleucid years, it would not have affected the linkage of years of Creation. It can be concluded that there is no living Samaritan tradition of linking the sequence of High Priests and years of Creation and Entry with absolute years. A.F. is not being used for dating these days. Here is another instance of the need for constant caution in handling modern Samaritan claims to possessing ancient traditional knowledge. There certainly is such knowledge and it must be sought out and used, but caution is needed. We might compare the modern dogma, first recorded in Chronicle Adler in 1900 or 1901, that there was never a Samaritan sanctuary building.

In the reckoning used by the authors of the Asaṭīr, which is traditional, the year running from late March of 36 to late March of 37 AD was a forty-ninth year. A Jubilee year started in late March of 37. [Year 1630 of counting for sabbatical years started in late March in 1 BC. See p. 4 top. Late March in 36 AD will be the start of year 1666 of counting. $[1,630 + 36 = 1,666]$. This was a forty-ninth year. $[34 \times 49 = 1,666]$. A forty-ninth year with the number 1666 would have seemed special, and it could naturally have been expected that the coming Jubilee Year running from late March of 37 AD to late March of 38 AD would be special. It would be natural to have special prayers over the three years before the Jubilee, starting in late March of 34 AD. The later part of the year 35 AD is the date of a massacre of Samaritans about to go up the Mountain. (The date of early 36 AD has been proposed but is unlikely. What is said in this paragraph about expectation of the Jubilee is not affected if the date is early 36 AD or even later in 36 AD. Because of this, the arguments for the different dates are not weighed up here). Josephus says this was by order of Pontius Pilate. This would have been just before the start of special public prayers for the manifestation of the occulted paraphernalia of the Mosaic Tabernacle, starting with public prayer on the Mountain on the fifteenth of the first. This was something that both parties, Dositheans and Sebuaeans, could wish for, even if only the Dositheans were concerned about having the original building reappear to replace the present building. Josephus lies and misleads. (*Antiquities*, XVIII:85–87 = 4:1 -- 2). See my book *A Samaritan Plan of Religious History*, pp. 95 -- 96.

The start of the seventh month of the religious year is usually at the end of September. Pilate did not get to Rome till after just after the death of Tiberius in mid March 37 AD. (Or he might have got there a few weeks after. See note 6). Even if we suppose that the massacre was at Passover in 36 AD, it still has to be explained why he didn't get to Rome till so much later. The usual explanation for this supposed long delay by Pilate is that the trip took more than a year. This is a stupid guess, repeated as if fact because someone said it. Plausibility does not get a thought. The trip usually only took a fortnight by commercial ship and could be done in a week by a fast government ship of the kind used for sending dispatches or carrying high officials. A common elaboration of the guess is that he must have gone by land. Not a thought as to why he would have been that silly, or would have defied orders. The seat of Roman government in Palestine was at Caesarea, so as to make communication with the city of Rome and travel to it by ship quick and easy. Going to Rome by land after being summoned would have been disobedience to the order to turn up straightaway, as well as plain silly. It still would not have taken this long even by land. There is a widespread attitude that if the answer to something is not known, you have to make something up, and if it is silly it doesn't matter. This is more than sloppiness, it is moral cowardice. It is not Wissenschaft either.

Pilate would have known about the usual pilgrimage at Passover and before the fifteenth of the seventh of the religious year. Besides this, he would have known a Jubilee year was coming. Whether it is the chronology of the Asaṭīr or the Tūlāda that is right, whether late 35 was in a forty-eighth year or a forty-ninth year, whether it was a forty-ninth year or a Jubilee year that started in late March of 36, there would have been special observances marking hopes and expectations long before the massacre. Pilate could not have been surprised. Josephus is hiding something really important. It seems he can't leave out what must have been common knowledge, so he misrepresents the significance, using deceptive omission, deceptive wording, and a couple of straight lies. We know the Samaritans were preparing to go up the Mountain to pray for the return of the Time of Favour, since a standard formula for the manifestation of the Mosaic paraphernalia of the Tabernacle hidden on the Mountain is quoted by Josephus. He deliberately misunderstands the syntax and adds a false gloss to get the reader to do the same. Everyone since has copied. Feldman's translation in the Loeb series goes against the syntax. He does not understand what Josephus means. See my book *A Samaritan Plan of Religious History* note 18 on p. 95. Unnecessary articles have been written saying the Samaritans must have thought Moses went to Mt. Gerizim, as if anything could be believed by Samaritans, even if contradicted by the Torah or plainly senseless. Feldman's mistranslation of the important sentence is always relied on, while claiming to know Greek. It is not Samaritans that can't think straight. Josephus says they expected immediate manifestation of the paraphernalia just by wishing for it, and says they followed a self-promoting religious loony. This has been believed in modern times, with the usual assertion that Samaritans are like that. See my book, p. 134. He does not quite say this pilgrimage was not at the usual time of a pilgrimage, but he does make sure to make the reader think that. In fact, in this place he tries to make the reader think there were never pilgrimages up the Mountain by a lot of people at once. This fits his consistent technique. Nowhere does he say what was on the Mountaintop in his day, not here or anywhere. In another place he says that what he asserts to have been the original sanctuary building was destroyed by Hyrcanus. He does not say no new building was put up, but makes sure to let any

careless reader think that. No modern authors except Montgomery have read his words properly and seen that he does not say no replacement was put up, but not even he saw that Josephus was playing tricks with words. See my book, pp. 109 – 110. The story that Pilate had armed men lurking in the crowd is unbelievable. If armed men had been lurking in the crowd, they would have had to be much less than half, so if the Samaritans were armed, it would have been the attackers that got killed. There is so much careful deception that **it can be doubted that it was Pilate that arranged the massacre**. It is more believable that companies of armed Jews attacked parties of Samaritans as they were on the way up the Mountain this time. It is believable that the Samaritans might have been armed because trouble could be expected. Although unprovable, the natural explanation of Josephus's odd silence on Pilate's delay in getting to Rome would be that there was long deep discussion between the Samaritan Senate and the Roman government on far-reaching changes of mutual benefit, and Pilate was recalled once the decision on separate administration of Samaria had been confirmed.

At Passover just after the start of an indeterminate year, but which looks to have been in 37 AD at the start of a Jubilee year (see note 6), there was an attempt by the Jewish religious authorities to get Jesus executed. A bare-faced threat of lying slander about Pilate was tried out, trying to coerce him. He did kill people whenever it suited him, but he saw no threat to Roman rule in Jesus. The Jewish religious authorities tried to frame Jesus by charging him with claiming to be king. It is quite possible that some Jewish revolutionaries had tried to revolt before the Jubilee year, and they used that to make their threat more impressive, because the Roman government would be on the lookout for any repeat. They were not believed by Pilate because he had learnt what the Jubilee was about and what was meant by a kingdom in the present in the world but not of the world. He wrote or said “Jesus the Nazor the King of the Jews” and made the notice or saying prominent. Exactly how this was done does not matter. Jesus has been split into two people, Jesus the Nazor and Jesus the son of the Rabban or religious authority. See my book of 2024, p. 68. He was released. The book of Acts twice says he was framed and judiciously murdered later by Jews. Pilate knew what the four words meant and took grim satisfaction in telling the Jewish religious authorities what they were not getting, self-government under them, the religious rulers. See my article *An Ancient Form of the Samaritan Concept of the Tā'eb*.

The religious authorities saw that Jesus claimed some special status, even if not publicly. Their reaction to his interpretation of a passage in Daniel does not help explain what was meant, because it could be an anachronism. Jesus's descent from David appears in two of the Gospels, but the concern is not followed up in the gospels, and in the writings attributed to Paul there is only a single mention, which is not used for anything. See Part II of my book. Making Jesus the expected Davidic king is a concern of modern Christian missionaries to Jews with a bad understanding of what Christianity is about. See the Excursus at the end of my book. What irked them might have been that Jesus was not concerned with having a nation-state ruled by either religious authorities or a king, and was actively promoting something else. “My kingdom is not of this world”. This definitely does not mean that he regarded the material world as unimportant, as misguided Christians under Gnostic influence have often done. “Except your righteousness exceed the righteousness of the scribes and Pharisees, ye shall in no case enter into the Kingdom of Heaven”. The word קָדַשׁ includes far more than personal piety. Jesus did not

think like a Christian. After these words addressed to the inner members of the Ebionites --- not outer members and not people in general --- come examples of how the mitsvot are to be carried out by them and only by them beyond the minimum requirements, with more intention. The inner members have a greater task than outsiders in working for the benefit of everyone, though the task is not theirs alone. The reader will immediately recognise that the same was said by one very early Jewish authority. (On the select audience of the Sermon on the Mount and the select but wider audience of the Sermon on the Plain, see p. 66 of my book in its context).

Now to the real concerns of Jesus in his use of the symbol of the Jubilee. This information is only brought in here because it can illuminate Samaritan hopes for the Jubilee. The information must be used with care because Jesus was not a Samaritan. The information can still be used because Jesus had close connections with the Samaritans and Galilean Jews in general were in social contact with them. See p. 67 of my book. As well as the information given there, there is the fact there were Samaritan Ebionites as well as Jewish ones. See my book, Part II section (e), pp. 41 to 44 middle, and see p. 66 middle. The term the Year of Favour is found in Isaiah and elsewhere, explicitly connected with the Jubilee. One might therefore speculate that the early Christian symbol of a fish originated as a hint at the number fifty. (This was pointed out to me by Stephan Herman Huller). The Aramaic word nūn means fish. The letter Nūn has the numerical value of fifty. This is not meant to exclude the intention of using the Greek word *ichthys* as an acronym of *Iēsous Christos Theou Hyios Sōtēr*. I think there is an allusion to Joshua the son of Nun as well, hitherto overlooked. The connection is explained in my article *An Ancient Form of the Samaritan Concept of the Tā'eb*. If such a connection is intended, then use of the symbol would have to have been very early, before the concept of the return of the Time of Favour had been replaced by the un-Israelite concept of Christ: that is to say it would have had to have been taken over by Christianity from the Ebionites. For the precise meaning of the term "Christianity", see the Excursus to my book of 2024. There were no Jewish Christians. The words are a contradiction in terms. There were Jewish and Samaritan followers of Jesus, **who did not teach Christianity or anything on the way to it**. I've been pointing this out for a long while but that didn't count because I haven't got a membership card. I now see that people with a proper licence are starting to say this, and coming from kosher mouths it is not rubbish. (I must acknowledge the work of Martijn Linszen in finding a lot of the data used in the Excursus. His work is even more useful than he realises. The argument for use of the term *chrēstós* by the Ebionites is mine).

The terms "Son of God" and "Saviour" are not necessarily Christian. If Israel is God's firstborn, as Moses was told to tell Pharaoh, then the person embodying Israel can be called the Son of God. This will be explained. The term "Saviour" could easily have been applied to the combined figure of Joshua as the unique agent of God after Moses and the Tā'eb as doing the work of Joshua, though such usage is not attested. What is attested is use of the name Joshua as a title by the Ebionites, with the meaning of one that with divine help had attained the level of Joshua, heretofore unique to him, and who was proof that others could profitably work towards getting closer to the same level and could aspire to it. See my book, p. 64. My own judgment is that such is the thought behind the words "And I, if I be lifted up, will draw all men unto me". This is judgment, not supposition. There is no need to suppose that the words were attributed to

Jesus by the early Church. The authenticity of the words is shown by the way the final editors of the gospel guess unconvincingly at the meaning, and then Christian theologians contradict the editors' guess by trying a different one. *If theirs is the right answer, why didn't the editors of the gospel know about it?* In general, what is called "high Christology" in this gospel is explicable as thought earlier than Christianity that was not understood any more, though obviously the final editors did their best to make all the bits fit what they thought. (There are undeniably a few late bits that showed late perspective when first put in). It would not be possible to posit Ebionite origin for the original form of the book, but it was less far removed from the Ebionites than Christianity is. This brings up the question of how much the Nazoraeans invented and removed themselves from the real Jesus and at the same time distanced themselves from the Ebionites in a different way, but this is not the place to go into any of that. It is still undeniable that the final form of the gospel of John is late and parts are alien to Judaism. See my article *An Ancient Form*, pp. 15 middle to 16, on the **phantom** lamb of God and Passover.

Now to the acronym and why it need not be an invention of the Christian Church. The term *christós* was read into the acronym by the Church, but this term was not originally in any verse of the NT. If this sentence is indigestible, read the Excursus to my book carefully. What is old is the term *chrēstós*. Christianity took this over from the Ebionites and others to give itself the trappings of Israelite religion, and then in about 185 A.D. changed it to the artificial word *christós*, which is not real Greek, regardless of what is taught in Christian theological colleges and glibly spouted. If this is indigestible as well, have a look at the Excursus to my book as well. (I know the term *christós* is in our mss. of Josephus to mean a pretender to rulership, but they were copied by Christians. Bauer can't find any use of the term by Pagans, and does acrobatics). For the meaning of the term *chrēstós*, see pp. 64 and 65 of my book. It is true that there is no extant attestation of use of the term by the Ebionites, but a plausible sign is given on p. 64 of my book. The meaning of the term is plainly given in the statement of doctrine on that page. One of the most obvious signs of use of the term in Christianity is Titus II:13 with the phrase "the appearing of the Glory of the great God and our saviour IS the XS". Remember the word *christós* or *chrēstos* is never spelt out in the NT. It is a useful rule to remember that the explanation of a verse or term in the NT that finds a deliberate echo of the Torah is to be treated as the right explanation. In the present case, Titus II:11, 13, 14 are meant to echo Deuteronomy XXXIII, and specifically verses 2 and 29. The verses in Titus say that if Jesus is Saviour, it is as the agent of God. The Glory of God is the manifestation of God. The theory is that the creative word or the Son is manifest in Jesus, as it says in John I:14 and 18, which echo Deuteronomy XXXIII:2. **This is not the Christian doctrine of the Incarnation.** This passage in Titus also shows the implication of the term "*chrēstós*" that was originally applied to Jesus. If Deuteronomy XXXIII is a blessing, it must refer to the future as well as the past. Verse 5 of Deuteronomy XXXIII in its future meaning refers to one that is King in the sense that Moses was (and not in the sense that David was). It says in Numbers XII and right at the end of Deuteronomy that Moses was given a unique degree of prophecy, directly from God without mediation by his own mind or personality. He was made King at Sinai, as verses 2 and 5 of Deuteronomy XXXIII say. This passage clearly implies that he embodies the whole twelve tribes. Notice the wording *אֲנִי יְהוָה* in the Samaritan. Moses gave Joshua part of his unique spirit of prophecy. This is how Jesus is thought to be King by nature. See my article *An Ancient*

Form of the Samaritan Concept of the Tā'eb. This is not at all the same thing as being descended from David, a very minor concept in the NT, and irrelevant to later christology. (Except in preaching to Jews by Evangelical Christians with no understanding of Christianity or Judaism). It will undoubtedly be objected that Jesus implicitly applied the term “anointed” to himself in his sermon at Capernaum (Luke IV:16--30). The answer to that is that he agrees with the Greek translation of Isaiah LXI:1 in interpreting the Hebrew term meaning “anointed” as having the spirit of God upon him. This spirit was in Joshua, the successor of Moses. (Numbers XXVII:18. Note that whereas the MT has “a man in whom is spirit”, the Samaritan has “the man”, that is, the only such man after the imminent death of Moses). Joshua was full of the spirit because Moses laid his hands upon him. Moses was full of the creative wisdom and in greater measure than Joshua. He was filled with it at Sinai. (This is the thought ultimately behind adoptionist Christianity, which is older than the doctrine of the Incarnation). Jesus spoke of someone anointed with the spirit of God, as said at the start of Isaiah XI and the start of Isaiah LXI and the start of Isaiah XLV, with different emphasis in each place.

This does not mean he ever used the term *christós* because whenever he needed to speak Greek he would have spoken real Greek. See the Excursus to my book of 2024 on this term. *Christos* means smeared all over or plastered in real Greek. The word is a back-formation from *Christianoi*, which itself was an artificial replacement of *Chrēstianoī*. It started off as a pejorative nickname, used by outsiders, from their constant marking of themselves with a *chrisma*. Adrian Grant was the first to see that this is documented in the writings of Theophilus of Antioch. This word *Christos* was never in the books now making up the NT. The mss. always have an abbreviation that could be read as *chrēstos* (or *chreistos*) and was in fact meant that way. This word *Christianoi* was taken over to replace the designation *Chrēstianoī*, which had become politically inconvenient. Latin-speakers did not notice how odd it sounded. Neither do graduates of Christian theological training institutions these days. Or the staff either.

Isaiah LXI:2 connects the Jubilee with the eschatological Day of Vengeance and Recompense in Deuteronomy XXXII:35, which it quotes as “To the Day [לְיוֹם] of Vengeance”, in agreement with the Samaritan text and the LXX (against MT “Mine [לִי] is vengeance”). This implies a great and final Jubilee, and thus a connection with Deuteronomy XXXIII read quite reasonably as being about a unique past figure and unique future figure. ⁷

⁷ This article is not about Christianity, but the following remarks are relevant to dating. Stephan Herman Huller has pointed out to me that there is a strong Patristic tradition that the first Easter Sunday was on March the 25th. It goes back to Alexander of Jerusalem writing in about 218 AD presumably with local knowledge; it also goes back to the chronographer Julius Africanus writing in about 221 AD, who has been acknowledged from Eusebius onwards as the unquestioned authority on chronology. This date is accepted by the Byzantine chronographers and historians. It is the traditional date in the Coptic Church. It would follow that the Last Supper would have been on the night of Thursday 22nd March. There is a difficulty. The fifteenth of Nisan fell on this day and date in 30 AD and 37 AD. The date of 30 AD is not quite impossible, but does not square with the indications that Jesus’s ministry was longer than usually thought. Given that Josephus’s story of Pilate’s recall is impossible for so many reasons, it has to be asked whether he got to Rome just after Tiberius died in mid March of 37, as Josephus hints (only hints), or whether he was recalled when preparations and planning for new administrative arrangements were underway after Tiberius had died. Either way, if the Christian tradition just mentioned is right, it would follow that John’s gospel is right in putting the Yom Tov of Passover on the Sabbath. This timing is

assumed in the liturgy of the Anglican Church and Roman Church for Saturday night after nightfall and complete dark. Exodus XV is read, and this passage belongs to the day after Passover. The time of the service is an assertion that the resurrection was at the end of the sabbath. (The eastern churches depart from Judaism in setting the start of the third day at midnight). There is still the difficulty of the record of the Last Supper on Passover on a Thursday night. The solution is that there really was a Last Supper on Thursday night at the start of the 14th of Nisan, but development in Christian doctrine identified the night with the night of Passover. **The Ebionite Gospel asserts a distinction between the Last Supper and Passover in the very place where Matthew, Mark, and Luke make them the same.** See my book of 2024, p. 43. Priority of a reading in the Ebionite Gospel is never to be lightly dismissed. Neither is priority of doctrine. This need not mean the reading is necessarily original, but it does mean it is likely to be closer to the original. The current doctrine identifying the two occasions has enormous difficulties. The Jesus of the Gospels speaks of a new covenant. Passover in Egypt was not the time of a covenant, and commemoration each year is not commemoration of a covenant. Christians looking at Judaism as Christians think there is a Passover sacrifice and write theological treatises and compose sermons. The real Jesus could not have equated eating his body and drinking his blood in symbolic form with eating mutton at Passover, because blood can never ever be consumed, not at Passover or any other time. Making it symbolic makes no difference. Christians can't grasp how alien Christianity is to Judaism. Misusing the Jewish scriptures only makes them deceive themselves. Besides, if the mutton is from a sacrifice, then so is the lettuce and crispbread. Jesus is not a lettuce in Christian theology. The mutton is not from a sacrifice anyway. The conclusion is that the liturgy of the Anglican Church and Rome has preserved an old symbolism and meaning of the death of Jesus against Matthew, Mark, and Luke. Even this depends on secondary identification of the Last Supper with Passover, however. Older than this is the concept of the bread and wine at the Last Supper as embodiment of the Christ, who is the embodiment of God. This concept itself is pagan, but looks like an adaptation of an important Israelite concept. **The words of institution fit Simon's concept of universal individual attainment of better embodiment of the creative Boundless Power with divine help, which is compatible with the religion of Israel.** The Great Power is quoted as speaking in the first person, the same as when the Great Thought says my yoke is easy and my burden light. (On the terms and the concept of progress see my book pp. 64 to 65 top and pp. 81 to 88). **All the same, it is not certain whether these words are authentic quotation of the Samaritan book, or show an Ebionite development.** Protestants make the bread and wine a memorial of the Christ as Jesus, not an embodiment, trying to remove correctly perceived deep incompatibility with the religion of Israel. They emphasise the slightly later concept of the death of Jesus as a sacrifice, and thus depart from the religion of Israel in a worse way. Development of this doctrine of sacrifice took time. The concept of the Atonement is in Paul's letters but not central. Where John's gospel mentions the lamb of God which taketh away the sins of the world the words say nothing about sacrifice unless you already think they do. Where the symbol comes from is impossible to say. The Lamb of God is made to evaporate in my article *An Ancient Form of the Samaritan Concept of the Tā'eb*. John never said anything about any lamb. The inventors of Christianity were not good at Aramaic. This explains why Christian theologians can't work out how to find this lamb in what they call the Old Testament. Now back to the dating. These years would have been when hope of the manifestation of the paraphernalia of the Mosaic Tabernacle was being promulgated. There could well have been Jews that had hopes for the long term. The subject of Jesus's sermon in Capharnaum long before this at the start of his ministry was the coming of the Year of Favour, the Jubilee Year. This sermon is the inaugural manifesto of a far-reaching plan and hope. An aside on the length of Jesus's public ministry. It is always asserted that this must have lasted either one year or three years. This is because it is said that the structure of Matthew, Mark, and Luke implies one year and the structure of John implies three years. This is not using judgment. Think of the number of followers Jesus is said to have had. What about the sending out of seventy-two emissaries for a long while? Whether it happened doesn't matter: the authors of these Gospels thought there was enough time. The ordering of the festivals mentioned in Matthew, Mark, and Luke according to the calendar does not have to mean the length of time was only one year. It might only be a literary device, or a way of ordering separate sayings and stories with no obvious relationship. The order of the festivals in John does not give you three years, but a minimum of three years.

Roman rule had always been favourable. Rule over Samaria by Jewish client kings had ended for good. The coming Jubilee Year could easily have been seen as the start of a new era, which had dawned with the setting up of the Samaritan Senate. By 35 AD the path to the start of the second Time of Favour with the manifestation of the paraphernalia of the Mosaic Tabernacle in the distant future had been cleared a little bit. There was plenty of time between late 35 AD or early 36 and the end of February in 37 AD for negotiations between the Samaritans and Rome. Pilate would have had to be recalled in February or March of 37 because administration of Samaria was about to be changed. Josephus's explanation is not believable, for reasons explained. In late 37 AD Roman government of Samaria was separated from government of Judaea and Galilea. Josephus would have had to say something about the events in 35 AD, as well as the separation of rule of Judaea and Samaria, because all this would have been common knowledge, but he does it deceptively and at the same time blatantly. He is believed these days. The readers that knew what he was doing would not have minded, and he would have known they knew. He manages to blame Pilate for the separation of rule of Judaea from rule of Samaria and take attention away from a far-reaching change in policy. He leaves out why the religious leaders in Judaea needed to be stopped from causing trouble outside Judaea. Sometimes he did not write for Romans.

After this, realistic plans for wellbeing under Roman rule start to be seen. Separation of the administration of Samaria from Judaea in late 37 AD was followed by the state visit of a Samaritan dignitary to Rome in the time of Claudius. The first year of Claudius in 41 AD might have been the first feasible time. Justin tried hard to make the visit seem not official and without long-term consequences. The falseness of the story can be seen in his firm statement that Simon addressed the Senate. He could not have made this up. It would not have been out of the ordinary to put up a statue in honour of a visiting dignitary whose cooperation in keeping his countrymen in good relations with Rome was being sought. Whether some confused over-religious person had seen a statue to the Sabine god Semo Sanco and told Justin he had seen a statue of Simon does not matter, since Justin's aggrieved tone shows he really believed it realistic that such a statue could have been put up by the Senate. The Samaritan representative might not have been called Simon. Someone could have seen the statue to Semo Sanco and misread the inscription and decided that the Samaritan representative must have been called Simon. Then Justin could have decided this must be the same Simon that he denounced, in spite of how implausible that was. (The author of the Samaritan book the *Apóphasis Megálē* might not have been called Simon either, except in the imagination of Christian higher-ups wanting to denounce it).

Full self-government under Roman suzerainty was reached under Hadrian at the latest, but more likely during the reign of Claudius. A person holding the position of Tetrarch over Samaria, who was also Patriarch of all Samaritans in Palestine and Phoenicia, was appointed by Hadrian near the end of his reign, as part of restoring order. The record in the extant text of A.F. and the Arabic Joshua book is debased, but the partial information given is enough to link the two. This person was called Bāba. That was his name. It is a well-attested diminutive in Samaritan usage. He was not called the gate. This common assertion depends on massive ignorance of Palestinian Aramaic. It also depends on ignorance of Jewish usage of names. It depends on laziness as well, since there are dictionaries of Rabbinic Hebrew with the form of

the name. Such is the usual standard of supposedly academic writing on Samaritans. Contrary to assertions from the commonly expressed assumption that Samaritans write fantasy, AF does not say Bāba Rabba ruled all Palestine, neither does he say he ruled any territory outside. He says he ruled over Samaria and everyone in it including Jews. At this time Samaria had its full territory northwards and southwards and along the coast. He says he was Patriarch of the Samaritans. He had jurisdiction over all substantial Samaritan communities in Palestine and southern Phoenicia. See my book of 2024, pp. 12 to 21. In my book in note 35 p. 160 I used the datum in the Tūlāda that Bāba died after the end of the year 4600 AM and showed that this means he died after late March of 174 AD and before late March of 175 AD. The Tūlāda makes him a High Priest and says he officiated for forty years. This figure can be taken literally, since it is in a list of High Priests with the length of their officiate. The start of his officiate would have been after late March in 134 AD. This would fit into the timetable of Hadrian's restoration of order during and after the Jewish revolt. He might have become ruler before 134.

Under Bāba's rule there was a systematic official effort to bring in the children and grandchildren of converts to Christianity. This was largely successful. Claims of discovery of Samaritan Christian synagogues coming out of the State of Israel depend on reading of Hebrew inscriptions according to the language of the twentieth century. Contrary to common belief, knowledge of Hebrew is not genetically transmitted. This kind of pseudo-science seems not to have gone away in 1945. In an article and his survey of 2016, Pummer copies previous writers in the State of Israel claiming their discovery of a Samaritan Christian synagogue while showing his own ignorance of Hebrew as he quotes them. The claims have been refuted by Yoram Tsafrir, who does know Hebrew earlier than its twentieth century form. His article appeared in 1979, but was never read by Pummer, who couldn't read it because it was in Hebrew.

Conditions were bad under Commodus and Septimius Severus. This was a break with tradition. Explanation is demanded. In my book of 2024, pp. 44 middle to 51 top, I argue that one main cause was purposeful deception by the Christian Church, first organised by Justin of Neapolis. It comes up throughout his writings, but is the whole message of his Second Apology in its extant form. It is addressed to the Senate leaving the Emperor out. That means it was probably written to be used by a faction in the Senate working against the Emperor's policy. He was probably executed for sedition against the Emperor, or as a menace to imperial order, or both at once. Christians were not persecuted at that time. After Septimius Severus, favourable rule by Rome kept up in fits and starts till eastern Christianity made itself the new Israel ruling the new Rome. The Christian Church used its hold over the government and the army to wage total war on Samaritan religion for three centuries, till Moslem rule gave relief.

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.ספר אסטיר (עם תרגום ופירוש) מאת זאב בן-היים. Tarbiz XIV:2, 1943, pp. 104 -- 125; XIV:3 -- 4, 1943, pp. 174 -- 190; XV:2, 1944, pp. 71 -- 87; 128. This article also has its own continuous numbering, though it was never separately published. See my book for detailed assessment.

I. R. M. Bóid, *The Transmission of the Samaritan Joshua-Judges*. DS-NELL (Leiden) vol. VI no. 1, 2004, pp. 1 -- 30. ISSN 1382--323X. On the Zenodo, Academia.edu, and ResearchGate websites. The primary account of the onset of the Fānūta and the signs of its coming in the last years of the Time of Favour are at the end of the Samaritan Joshua book, after the list of the Kings (called Judges in the Jewish record). This book was originally written in Hebrew. It was translated into Aramaic with some abridgment to suit the new purpose of giving a detailed explanation of the cause of the end of the Time of Favour, in a form that both the Sebuacaeans and Dositheans could agree on. It survives in an Arabic translation. There is a late dreary apocryphal insertion defeating the purpose of the book. There are late additions of excerpts from a bad fictionalised history at the end. The text has had very late bad editing.

I. R. M. Bóid, *A Samaritan Plan of Religious History*. First edition 2023, second revised and expanded edition 2024. On the Zenodo, Academia.edu, and ResearchGate websites. Gives all information that might be needed to see the context of the subject of this article. Part VII is on the state of the text of the book by A.F. and the considerations to be borne in mind by anyone ever using it.

I. R. M. Bóid, *An Ancient Form of the Samaritan Doctrine of the Tā'eb*. 2025. On the Zenodo, ResearchGate, and Academia.edu websites.

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התולדה. כרוניקה שומרונים.מקור. תרגום. פירוש. ההדיר משה פלורנטין. הוצאת יד יצחק בן-צבי, ירושלים, תשי"ס .1999 .ISBN 965-217-169--7

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A. С. Жамкочян, *Самаритянская Хроника Абу-л-Фатха из Собрания Российской Национальной Библиотеки*. Moscow 1995. ISBN 5-7262-0203--1. The only accurate translation into any language. An exemplar given by me is in the NINO library. A pdf can be downloaded from my colleague Helen Gael's Profile page on the Academia website. For dishonest political reasons, this translation is not mentioned by Reinhard Pummer in his supposed complete survey entitled *The Samaritans: A Profile*, published in 2016. Note added in December 2025. For the whole sordid story and the broader picture see the entry on this translation in the bibliography to my article *Samaritan Essenes*, which is up on the ResearchGate and Academia websites.

Chronicon Samaritanum, Arabice conscriptum, cui titulus est Liber Josuae, ed. T. G. J. Juynboll, Leyden 1848. Arabic title-page سفر يوشع بن نون عليه السلام. There is a Latin translation. This is the primary source for the explanation of the ending of the Time of Favour. For the English translation by Crane, which is good but not quite always accurate enough, see the entry for Juynboll's edition in the Bibliography to my book.

John Macdonald, *The Theology of the Samaritans*. SPCK Press, London, 1964. Highly useful but not to be relied on by itself for important conclusions. Change over time is not adequately brought out. The fourteenth century is over-represented because the book is partly a reproduction of a doctoral thesis on the writings of this time by R. J. F. Trotter, Leeds 1961, without acknowledgment. Macdonald showed better judgment than Trotter, though. He did not accept Trotter's belief that Samaritan religion had been strongly influenced by Christianity, which came partly from not knowing enough about Judaism, partly from seeing signs of Christian thought that were not there. This book is the last of Macdonald's writings with mostly sound judgment.

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Paul Stenhouse, *The Kitāb al-Tarīkh [sic] of Abū 'l-Fath*. Sydney 1985. No ISBN. This is a translation. Listed here only as a warning, because it is unsafe to use even where it seems to make sense. The translator did not know basic Arabic syntax and morphology. Some ordinary words are not recognised. Words are sometimes invented. Some translations are quite literally a departure from rationality. This statement must be heeded. Sometimes the translator follows an emendation by Vilmar against all the mss. and against the information in his own thesis, not on purpose, but out of carelessness, without noticing. The translation was made before the doctoral thesis was done, and though there was some revision against the information in the thesis, it was scatty, to the extent of letting the translation contradict the argument of the notes to the text in the thesis in many places. See my book, Part VII, at great length on all this, with examples.

Abulfathi Annales Samaritani quos ad Fidem Codicum Manu Scriptorum Edidit et Prolegomenis Instruxit Eduardus Vilmar. Gotha 1865. Arabic title-page كتاب التاريخ مما تقدم عن الابا. The only published edition. Very good, but needs to be used with care, because the editor was never able to finish revising it. Nevertheless, the text printed by Vilmar is better than the text lying behind Stenhouse's translation. See my book, Part VII, on all this. Vilmar gives a long detailed summary that will do instead of a translation for some purposes.